
WUR_DMPProtocol_TemplateAndGuidance_v13-01

Authors: Irene Verhagen
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5588-1333>

Eri van Heijnsbergen
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1266-6291>

Date: 20260317

Organization: Wageningen University & Research
<https://ror.org/04qw24q55>

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WUR data management protocol template

The WUR data management protocol template can be used for outlining the general research data management practices agreed upon within a chair group (WU) / business unit (WR). When using this template, fill in the required information at [...].

- This template adheres to the [WUR data policy](#) requirements.
- A data management protocol is a 'living document' and, as such, can be edited and updated at any time. An annual review of the data management protocol is considered good practise.
- You are free to add (a) header(s) to this template to better align with the requirements of your research group, but the original headers should be retained.
- Answers provided are suggested texts / examples and can be tailored to the data management practices within the research group as long as compliance to the WUR data policy is maintained.
- To get to additional information in the appendix for each section, hold keyboard key CTRL + left-click [\[info\]](#) or right-click [\[info\]](#) and select 'open hyperlink'.
- Do you need support creating this protocol? Depending on the topic, please, contact data@wur.nl, your [privacy or information security officer](#), your [legal department](#), your [\(coordinating\) data steward](#), or visit <https://www.wur.eu/rdm> for more information.

Data management protocol - [name research group]

Title of document	Data management protocol [name research group]
Document first drafted	[date in YYYYMMDD]
Date of update + version	[date in YYYYMMDD + vxx (e.g. 20230309_v01)]
Previous versions	[list dates and version of previous versions of this protocol]
Document approved by	[name(s)]
Data management protocol created and written by	[name(s)]
Contact	[data steward contact name + email] [coordinating data steward contact name + email] [research group secretariat contact name + email] [information security officer contact name + email] [privacy officer contact name + email]

1. Definitions and abbreviations (alphabetic order)

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation.
Head of research group	Chair holder / business unit manager.
ISO	Information security officer.
Personal data	Any information which can identify a living individual.
PO	Privacy officer.
RDM	Research data management.
Research data (underlying publications)	Research data encompasses all information and / or resources required to reproduce the results and conclusions of research and includes, but is not limited to]: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Raw data (where legally allowed, e.g. according to the GDPR).• Processing and analysis scripts.• Processed / cleaned data where required, e.g. when scripts are not sufficient or available.• Analysed data where required, e.g. when scripts are not sufficient or available.• Source code and software developed during the research project.• Data documentation and metadata, which includes minimally the WUR recommendations. [add when applicable].
Research group	Chair group (WU) / business unit (WR).
Research Software	Research Software includes source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose.
WR	Wageningen Research.
WU	Wageningen University.
WUR	Wageningen University and Research.

2. Purpose [\[info\]](#)

The purpose of this data management protocol is to outline agreed upon general data management practices applicable to all research data produced within research projects performed within **[name research group]**. This includes research data derived within BSc / MSc thesis projects, PhD thesis projects, postdoc projects, staff projects, as well as other research projects.

The outlined data management practices aim to prevent data loss, increase safe handling of personal or otherwise sensitive data, and increase reusability of data by complying with the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, GDPR, WUR information security and WUR data policy. The WUR data policy is guided by, amongst others, the FAIR principles and the motto to share data 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. For links, see chapter 3.

3. Links to information used

Policies / guidelines

- [WUR data policy](#)
- [Information security policy](#)
- [Data classification](#)
- [Data sharing guidelines](#)
- [Privacy policy](#)
- [Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#)
- [FAIR principles](#)
- [GDPR](#)

Software / apps and storage media

- [Storage finder](#)
- [Repository finder](#)
- [ApprovedApps tool](#)
- [DMPonline](#)

Research data and software management support

- [Research data and software management info](#)
- data@wur.nl
- [\(Coordinating\) data stewards](#)

Templates

- [Data management plan \(students\)](#)
- [Software management plan](#)
- [Metadata and data documentation](#)
- [Yoda metadata editor](#)

Privacy, security, legal support

- [SmartPIA](#)
- [Data rightsholder](#)
- [Privacy and information security officers](#)
- [Legal departments](#)

Data stewardship

- [Data steward tasks](#)

4. Roles and responsibilities [\[info\]](#)

Who	Roles and responsibilities at [name research group]
Head of research group [name head of research group]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compliance with the WUR data policy. • Creates a data management protocol or delegates the creation to e.g. the data steward. • Ensures a data steward is present. • Ensures a contact point for the appropriate handling of data access requests for data published restricted access or archived by the research group.
Data Steward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiates, (co)-creates and updates the data management protocol and provides advice to and / or consults the management / head of the research group. • Functions as a primary contact point to research group for questions and advice about data management (plans) and refers them to (data management) support when necessary. • Communicates the WUR data policy and data management protocol to (new) members of the research group. • [Optional: add other research group specific tasks / responsibilities].
Researcher Any researcher (e.g. PhD candidate, postdoc, associate professor, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manages data properly and safely during the entire life cycle of the research project, complying with WUR and, when applicable, external policies. • Preserves data underlying (a) publication(s) or (a) report(s) after the research project in an appropriate storage medium or data repository. • Registers data underlying (a) publication(s) or (a) report(s) in Pure via an email to data@wur.nl. • [Optional: add other research group specific tasks / responsibilities].
PhD candidate Additional responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Writes a DMP within 6 months of the start of their PhD (upload in Hora Finita). • Have their DMP checked by their supervisor(s) and / or data steward. A DMP review is recommended: request a review via data@wur.nl or request feedback via DMPonline. • Consults with the supervisor when others are requesting access to the data during and after research. • [Optional: add other research group specific tasks / responsibilities].

<p>Supervisor</p> <p>Additional responsibilities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supervises the writing of a data management plan by a PhD candidate or MSc / BSc thesis student (when applicable). Guides proper and safe data management during the research project of PhD candidates and / or students. Co-authorises others for read / write access to the data (folders and / or files) and ensures they are up to date. [Optional: add other research group specific tasks / responsibilities].
<p>BSc/MSc student</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Registers their MSc thesis in Osiris and acknowledges the thesis agreement in Osiris. Uses storage solutions and software used within the research group (see 'Safe and shareable storage during research' below) that match the classification of the data. For example, solutions provided by WUR and / or in the ApprovedApps tool. Requests approval from their supervisor to share data or store data outside of WUR managed platforms. Ensures careful handling of any personal or otherwise sensitive data during and after the thesis. Transfers data to their supervisor when the project is finished. This only applies when [name research group] is leading in supervising the thesis. [Optional: add other group specific tasks / responsibilities].
<p>Other</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [Optional: add other group specific tasks / responsibilities].

5. Data (rights)holder, sharing and accessibility [\[info\]](#)

Suggested text (can be adopted / tailored): WUR is (rights)holder to all data, software and / or models created during research by its employees and non-employee PhD candidates, excluding BSc and MSC students. Unless otherwise stipulated in a consortium agreement or contract between WUR and other parties. Sharing of and accessibility to the data, software and / or models created by **[name research group]** will be arranged on a case-to-case basis in consultation with the legal department where required and depends on sensitivity and contractual obligations. When data, software and / or models are created by a party other than WUR, the policies of that party should be consulted and adhered to, e. g. such as (rights)holder policies. When data, software and / or models are being reused, their licences are adhered to.

6. Safe and shareable storage during research [\[info\]](#)

Suggested text / table (can be adopted / tailored): Research data, code and scripts need to be stored safely. To do so, research data first needs to be classified (e.g. negligible, some, serious or disruptive). Storage solutions provided by WUR are suitable for data classified up to serious. When other software is needed to collect / process data, check the ApprovedApps tool. **Do NOT store research data for long term on hard disks, USBs, personal laptops. Do not use third party cloud services such as Google Drive and Dropbox.**

To get support with classifying data and when a research project involves serious or disruptive research data contact your Information Security Officer for additional measures.

During research: where should data, code and scripts be stored?	
Storage location(s) used within [research group]	<p>[e.g. W:\xxx\xxx...; Git@WUR project repository address; Yoda@WUR research-xxx-xxx and vault-xxx-xxx]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> At all times the raw and an up to date version of the research data are securely stored on above mentioned storage location(s) to ensure continuity of access. OneDrive, Teams and M-drive are only used transiently for working copies, because upon termination of a WUR account, all files on OneDrive and / or the M-drive are automatically and permanently deleted. A Teams channel will be deleted after a year of inactivity. Personal or otherwise sensitive data on hardware or platforms required for collection, processing, or analysis purposes, is removed as soon as possible from those platforms and hardware (after the data is safely transferred to the above mentioned storage solution(s)).
Sharing with project members	<p>[e.g. WUR Teams, WUR OneDrive, institutional mail, Yoda@WUR, SURFfilesender]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Before sharing data with project members, the data classification and data sharing guidelines are taken into account to determine whether the data can be shared and on which platform.
[add other requirements where applicable]	

7. Data preservation and registration after research [\[info\]](#)

Suggested text / table (can be adopted / tailored): Depending on the data classification, the rightsholder(s), contractual and ethical obligations, licences, and policies (see WUR data sharing guidelines, link in chapter 3) research data is preserved via archiving at WUR [[W:drive / Yoda / Tape](#)] or publishing in a data repository (see WUR repository finder) in preferred formats where possible (for examples see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>). When not possible, the research data documentation (see 'Data documentation and metadata' below) will describe contents of the data and the used software (including version and provider of software).

Data underlying publications (articles / reports / theses) include all files required for reproducing research results and conclusions (see definition chapter 1). Data underlying publications is preserved (archiving or publishing) and registered (see below) to enable verification of the research and reusability of the data. When published, a discipline specific repository is preferred (see WUR repository finder). If no discipline specific repository is available, data is published in [[e.g. DANS Data Stations, 4TU.ResearchData, Zenodo, \(and Yoda@WUR in the future\)](#)]. When published with restricted access, a data sharing agreement is set up. Additionally, the primary contact point for data requests is [[names and email addresses of contact](#)] which will oversee evaluation of requests and providing access. When data underlying publications cannot be published, it is archived and the metadata is published (for example the Yoda metadata).

A version of code / scripts in a Git platform that has been used underlying a publication is published as well by downloading the main branch of the project repository and publishing it in a data repository. The main branch can be published with any data or be published as a separate publication. This ensures that any links provided remain usable. Hence, it is good practice to at least download the master branch of your project repository and add it to the research data files where possible.

Data not underlying publications are encouraged to be published, when possible (see WUR data sharing guidelines) and registered. For source code and scripts not underlying a research data file publication, it is recommended to download the main branch from Git@WUR and add to the research data to be archived.

Registration of [data](#) and [software](#) is performed through an email to [[e.g. email address secretariat, \[data@wur.nl\]\(mailto:data@wur.nl\)](#)] which includes:

- The persistent identifier of or pathway to the data.
- References or persistent identifiers to the accompanying publication(s) (journal or report).
- Creator / author name(s).
- Metadata (minimally the [WUR recommendations](#)).

If applicable, research models can be registered in the [WUR model gallery](#).

8. Data documentation and metadata [\[info\]](#)

Suggested text / table (can be adopted / tailored):

Documentation: both data that is published in a repository or archived at WUR (e.g. W:drive, Yoda, Tape) should be accompanied by documentation in the form of a README.txt file. The minimum information supplied in the documentation will be equivalent to the WUR readme and codebook template (see [this page](#) and DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7701727](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7701727)).

Metadata: when a discipline specific metadata standard is available and known or a discipline specific repository is used that incorporate their own metadata standard, those metadata standards will be applied [\[please list the metadata standards \(can be found at e.g. \[schema.org\]\(https://schema.org\) or \[fairsharing.org\]\(https://fairsharing.org\)\)\]](#). When publishing data in a general repository, such as DANS Data Stations, 4TU.ResearchData or Zenodo, the metadata standard of that repository is used to describe the data. When there is (i) no discipline specific metadata standard, (ii) the data repository only allows limited metadata, or (iii) the data is archived internally at WUR, the minimum required metadata to be applied will be the Yoda metadata terms based on the Datacite metadata standard. These metadata can be created from within Yoda@WUR or through the [Yoda metadata editor](#) (when the Yoda@WUR platform is not being used by the group).

9. Data / software management plans for PhD candidates / research projects [\[info\]](#)

Suggested text / table (can be adopted / tailored):

Data management plan

As research funders do not make their data management plan templates mandatory to use, the WUR data management plan template is filled in using [DMPonline](#). A manual to create an account and data / software management plan is available via DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7073740](#). It is recommended, and usually mandatory when a funder is involved, to request a review of the data management plan in DMPonline. PhD candidates are required to have a data management plan and have it submitted within 6 months of starting their project. In general, the data management plan should be updated and maintained throughout the research project when changes in data management practices are made.

DMP for MSc students

Though not mandatory, [\[name research group\]](#) recommends having MSc students fill in the WUR MSc DMP template (with their supervisor(s)). This template is available via DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12805038](#).

Software management plan

Though not mandatory (yet), [\[name research group\]](#) recommends researchers to write a [software management plan](#) in DMPonline when Research Software that can potentially be reused within other research projects or decision-making processes is created during a research project.

Feel free to add (a) header(s) (if applicable)

Appendix: additional information

(may be deleted after completion)

Answers provided above are examples and can be tailored to the data management practices within the research group as long as compliance to the WUR information security and data policy is maintained.

Info: 2. Purpose

A group may choose to have the data management protocol also apply to BSc / MSc students.

Info: 4. Roles and responsibilities

Identifying persons who are (or can be) of assistance in data management practices helps to clarify the data collection process within the research group. Identifying these roles are also important when employees / PhD candidates / students must hand over the data to WUR in the event of leaving WUR. In the table several (potential) roles and responsibilities have been provided. For information about data classifications, find the link in chapter 3.

Info: 5. Data (rights)holder, sharing and accessibility

Explain, in general, what the procedures / guidelines are considering the data rights(holder), data sharing and accessibility within the research group when:

1. Data is collected solely by WUR (employees).
2. Data is collected from / with / on behalf of third parties (other than WUR).
3. Data is provided by a third party (other than WUR).

WUR is the rightsholder of the research data and entitled to data(bases) created by any WUR staff member within the scope of their employment. This means that WUR researchers are not the owner nor right holders of the data(base).

[WUR as rightsholder](#) should be discussed in the case the funder of the project, i.e. a third party (either public or commercial), imposes ownership / rightsholder conditions. This discussion takes place before the project starts. E.g. partner funding can condition that the data will become under (shared) ownership of the partners / partners are (shared) rightsholder. In this case a consortium agreement or a data sharing agreement should be agreed upon before starting the project, where required, in consultation with the [legal department](#).

The party that is the rightsholder of the data decides what others are allowed to do with it; e.g. how the data is shared, and accessibility to the data. If you collect data from / with

/ on behalf of an external party, you may have other agreements (e.g. consortium agreement, data sharing agreement) with that party, and these generally overrule WUR's IP Policy & Value Creation. The [research data sharing guidelines](#) can help with this.

Info: 6. Safe and shareable storage during research

Describe the general procedures / guidelines for data storage during research within the research group. If there are general pathways on the W-drive or Yoda@WUR, these can be added as well.

Ensure that storage practices within the research group comply with the WUR's data policy and the [Information Security policy](#) (e.g. [data classification](#)). Safe and shareable storage of data following these policies means storing research data (including code etc.) and data documentation during research on (a) [storage solution\(s\)](#) provided by WUR (and thus managed by WUR). Note that WUR's storage solutions are backed up automatically and data recovery is in place. Check the [ApprovedApps tool](#) when other software is needed to collect / process data. Any questions regarding the above mentioned can be addressed to your [information security officer](#).

Note that all WUR employees and users need to properly and safely handle and store research data, but appropriate platforms may not be available by default for all users. For example, MSc and BSc students do not have access to all WUR managed solutions / platforms or hardware for handling and storing of (personal or otherwise sensitive) data. Specific arrangements must be made for these groups of WUR users.

Info: 7. Data preservation and registration after research

Describe the general practices for preserving and registering data within the research group.

WUR's data policy stipulates that research data underlying publications (articles, reports, theses) must be preserved for at least ten years, if possible, in a data repository. Repositories are online archiving services that preserve data safely and make them findable. Data can be archived publicly, and with restricted access. However, there could be legitimate reasons not to deposit data in a repository, but to archive the data on the W-drive / Yoda@WUR / tape storage (or archive the data with a third party owning / being the rightsholder of the data): there is personal or otherwise sensitive data, company interest involved etc.), WUR is not the rightsholder, Intellectual Property Rights, the data volume is too big etc. The research [data sharing guidelines](#) can help in setting the general practices within the research group for sharing research data.

The data underlying publications that are preserved should, also in compliance with the WUR data policy, be registered in Pure. Registration can be done by sending an email to data@wur.nl with the persistent identifier (e.g. DOI, accession number) or link / pathway to the data and

associated metadata. To link the data to the accompanying publications, the publications involved and their links / DOIs need to be specified as well. Library staff will then ensure your research output is properly linked and becomes visible in [Research@WUR](#).

Info: 8. Data documentation and metadata

Describe the general procedures / guidelines how data should be documented within the research group. Outline the metadata that will accompany the data within the research group and whether there are metadata standards to be used. It is possible to make a distinction between BSc / MSc projects and other projects.

It is essential to systematically [document](#) data during research, when archiving data internally (e.g. at WUR) and when depositing data in an online repository to make data understandable, discoverable, citable and reusable. The most common required form of documenting research data is by adding a readme file, which is further supplemented with metadata. Independently of where data is preserved (e.g. at WUR, in a data repository) it should be accompanied by:

- a readme file

The readme file contains information about e.g. the steps that have been undertaken in processing and analysing data. In short: all information necessary to understand the data, reproduce research and verify results. WUR Library advises to use the WUR readme file template as the minimum required documentation to add to the data. Feel free to add more documentation where appropriate and required.

- metadata

Metadata is machine-readable information about the data, according to fixed terms, which makes the data findable and searchable. WUR Library advises to use the Yoda metadata terms as the minimum required metadata to add to the data. You can fill in these terms in Yoda, when applicable as a storage solution, or use the Yoda metadata editor and download the metadata as a .json file.

- a codebook

WUR Library advises to use the WUR codebook template to explain variables, abbreviations, etc, because this template is in .csv format, which makes it easy to import into software such as R, Python, etc.

The templates for the readme file and codebook can be found here DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7701727](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7701727). Via this link a filled in example of a readme file, codebook and metadata file can be found as well.

Info: 9. Data / software management plans for PhD candidates/research projects

Describe the guidelines for how data and / or software management plans are implemented in the research group.

The WUR data policy stipulates that every PhD candidate should have a data management plan. The policy applies to WU, but not to WR. However, we highly recommend data management plans for any research project regardless of function or organisation. To date, there are no known funders that make their own templates mandatory. Also, it happens that the funder does not have a template available. In these cases, we strongly advise to use the WUR DMP template (see below) as it much better aligns to services and practices at WUR.

Further, we encourage MSc students to write a data management plan. Although not mandatory at WUR, filling in a data management plan would create awareness with students about good data management practices. This could be invaluable not only during their thesis, but also in their future careers.

When Research Software is being developed during a project, with the intent for others to reuse in their own project or workflow, the research software is classified as medium to high maintenance. Then, although not (yet) mandatory at WUR, it is advised to describe the research software in a software management plan.

A data or software management plan is a 'living' document in which data and software management practices on the project level are described. The following WUR templates with accompanying guidance are available as a published document and in DMPonline (recommended):

- WUR data management plan template via DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7233369](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7233369).
- WUR software management plan template via DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10473645](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10473645).
- WUR MSc data management plan template via DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12805038](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12805038).